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STATISTICAL ANALYSIS OF TOTAL POPULATION INCOME IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract: This study conducts a statistical analysis of total population income in the Republic of Uzbekistan by examining its structure, dynamics, and key determinants using official statistical data. The findings offer policy recommendations aimed at promoting income equality and improving overall economic well-being.

Key words: total income, Uzbekistan, income distribution, per capita income, household income, statistical analysis, economic growth, inequality.

INTRODUCTION

Income serves as a fundamental indicator of economic well-being, influencing living standards, social stability, and broader economic development. In recent years, Uzbekistan has prioritized economic reforms and modernization, with particular emphasis on improving household income levels. Analyzing population income is essential for assessing economic welfare, identifying disparities across social groups and regions, and informing evidence-based economic and social policies. A comprehensive evaluation of income distribution enables policymakers to gauge living standards, mitigate inequality, and promote sustainable economic growth.

Gross income, a key measure of welfare, encompasses earnings from labor, self-employment, property (e.g., interest, dividends), and transfers (e.g., pensions, social benefits, remittances). Per capita gross income – calculated as the ratio of total income to population size – provides a comparative metric for evaluating living standards across regions and nations [2].

To address regional employment challenges, stimulate entrepreneurship, and enhance social support for vulnerable groups, the government has implemented targeted policies. Notably, the Presidential Decree No. PP-12 (January 17, 2025), “On Measures to Ensure Employment and Poverty Reduction in 2025”¹ outlines strategies for job creation, income growth, and poverty alleviation through efficient resource allocation and social benefit optimization [8].

LITERATURE REVIEW

Income is a broad concept that includes any material or financial wealth received by the population. In this regard, various economists and scholars have proposed different theories on this issue, each interpreted based on its own approach and characteristics. American economist Simon Kuznets, in his “Kuznets Curve” theory, argues that income inequality increases with economic growth, but later decreases [3]. Among Uzbek researchers, Professor Shodmonov Sh. defines population income as “the amount of money and in-kind receipts received by individuals over a certain period (for example, a year).” He also emphasizes that “the concepts of nominal and real income are used to assess the population’s income level” [4]. Nominal income refers to the amount of income received by the population in monetary form over a given time period. Real income refers to the quantity of goods and services that can be purchased with the disposable income of the population. In essence, real income reflects the purchasing power of individuals [5]. Abdurahmanov Q.Kh., Abdurahmanov X.Kh., and Qurboniyozov I.R., in their textbook *Social Protection of the Population*, emphasize that population income means “the material and spiritual well-being of a person depends on his income. The higher a person’s income, the greater the opportunities to meet basic needs, maintain health, engage in recreation, access education, and spend leisure time culturally” [6].

¹ <https://www.lex.uz/uz/docs/-7327821>

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In conducting this analytical work, standard methods from the scientific research methodology were employed. Throughout the process of scientific analysis, various techniques such as observation, generalization, classification, comparison, and analytical methods were utilized extensively. Additionally, statistical, graphical, and synthesis methods were applied to ensure a comprehensive evaluation.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

On the one hand, the reforms carried out in our country are aimed at increasing the income of the population and improving their standard of living. On the other hand, they focus on reducing disparities in income levels among the population. At the end of the nine-month period, the real income of the population increased by 7.7% compared to the same period in 2023. Total per capita income increased by 15.5% (including an inflation rate of 5.5%), reaching 17.4 million [2].

Picture 1. Total income of the population, billion soums.²

Looking at the data in Picture 1, the level of total income of the population in the Republic of Uzbekistan has shown a gradual upward trend. From approximately 250,000 billion soums in 2017, the figure rose to about 987,000 billion soums by 2024 – more than a threefold increase over eight years. This long-term upward trend reflects improved economic conditions and possibly rising employment and wages.

Today, the regular growth of the population in our country and the observed territorial differences in the volume of per capita income further increase the need for research into the volume of general surveys.

Table 1. Total per capita income volume (in the cross section of territories), thousand soums.³

No	Regions	2023	2024	Change in 2024 compared to 2023, %
1	Karakalpakistan Republic	15037,5	16858	12,1
2	Andijan	19236,1	21926,3	14,0
3	Bukhara	24267,7	27508	13,4
4	Jizzakh	17389,2	19435,1	11,8
5	Kashkadarya	16366,7	18473,5	12,9
6	Navoiy	32537	38112,3	17,1
7	Namangan	15291,1	16849	10,2
8	Samarkand	16701,5	19215,4	15,1

2 Analyzed by the author based on data provided by the official website of the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

3 Analyzed by the author based on data provided by the official website of the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

9	Surkhandarya	16205,8	17880	10,3
10	Sirdarya	16954,9	19036,5	12,3
11	Tashkent region	21563,1	25123,3	16,5
12	Fergana	17320,7	19119,9	10,4
13	Kharazm	20509,2	23410,8	14,1
14	Tashkent city	47183,4	60594,4	28,4
	Total:	20764,5	24111,9	16,1

From the table analyzed above, we can see that the volume of total per capita income in the territory of Uzbekistan between 2023 and 2024 showed significant changes. Total per capita income in 2023 was 20,764.5 thousand soums, while in 2024 this figure increased to 24,111.9 thousand soums. This represents a 16.1% increase in total per capita income over one year. In some provinces, this rate decreased significantly, while in others, the change was relatively moderate.

The region with the most significant increase in the period 2023–2024 was the city of Tashkent, where per capita income rose from 47,183.4 thousand to 60,594.4 thousand soums (28.4%). In the same year, Navoiy, Tashkent, and Samarkand regions ranked next with higher per capita income levels. These regions saw increases of 17.1%, 16.5%, and 15.1%, respectively. This growth is attributed to the implementation of large industrial enterprises and production projects in these areas, which helped boost income levels.

It should also be noted that the lowest increase was recorded in the Namangan, Surkhandarya, and Fergana regions, where the average per capita income of 17,111 thousand soums increased by only 10.3% in one year.

According to the World Bank, the Gini coefficient – a measure of economic inequality – in Uzbekistan in 2022 was 0.31 [9]. This indicator is closely related to population income and wages.

Picture 2. Average monthly salary by region in 2023, soums.⁴

Looking at the above-analyzed figure, in 2023, the average salary in Tashkent city was around 6 million soums, and in the Navoi region around 5 million soums, recording the highest levels compared to other regions. This is because industry, infrastructure, and services are well developed in these regions. However, the lowest figures were recorded in the Namangan, Fergana, and Samarkand regions, with average salaries amounting to 2,786,311 soums, 2,853,149 soums, and 2,853,459 soums, respectively.

It is clear that such large differences contribute to economic inequality in our country. At the same time, the monthly salary directly affects the overall income of the population.

⁴ Analyzed by the author based on data provided by the official website of the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

CONCLUSION

Incomes of the population not only determine material well-being but also reflect the efficiency of the economy and the state of economic relations in society. Therefore, in order to improve the living standards of citizens and create profitable employment opportunities in the labor market, it is necessary to pay special attention to increasing the total income of the population. In particular, to address existing and similar shortcomings, the following proposals are recommended: creating jobs in high-income sectors based on new technologies and increasing the overall employment rate; supporting family entrepreneurship; generating income from land through the rational use of agricultural land resources; and expanding opportunities for earning income through housing and real estate. If these measures are effectively implemented, the well-being of the population in Uzbekistan will improve further, and total household income will rise to a significantly higher level.

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